

Primer: File Naming Conventions

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What is a File Name Convention?

A file naming convention (FNC) can be defined as a structured framework that incorporates relevant information into the file name. A filename typically includes a name and an [extension](#), the latter indicating the format of the file, the former typically referring to relevant metadata. An FNC is an agreement on how to save files in an organized and transparent manner. This primer focuses on FNCs with a focus on research data. A meaningful FNC enables you to understand the content outlines of a file without opening it. Therefore, it enhances findability and reproducibility and helps researchers to easily navigate through their data repositories.

Why is it relevant?

Early on, information scientists recognized the necessity of establishing naming schemes for files and images ([Crowder et al., 2015](#)). A good FNC leads to an organized and accessible collection of files by making it easier to browse through lengthy lists of files and identify missing or relocated files. Therefore, a well-defined FNC enhances the reproducibility of data on three different levels. First, on a personal level, it enables researchers to search and retrieve their own data, especially when revisiting it after a considerable period of time, e.g. for revisions. Second, within a research or project group, consistent file naming assists co-workers in effectively continuing to work with the data. Third, on the level of external researchers who lack internal knowledge of the project, a standardized FNC facilitates the discovery and access of the correct data. Agreeing upon the FNC during the research design phase pays off during data collection by reducing the need for error corrections during storage. Additionally, it improves findability during analysis and the revision phase. Overall, implementing an effective FNC from the outset of a research project ensures better data organization, accessibility, and reproducibility, aligning with the FAIR principles for data management ([Wilkinson et al., 2016](#)) and facilitating collaboration among researchers.

What to include in an FNC?

To benefit from FNCs across the three levels, an FNC should be established in a meaningful, consistent and unique manner. Different research disciplines deal with various types of data, so FNCs tend to be specific to a discipline or purpose. However, there are general agreements on FNCs. Universities, libraries and archives often provide their own guidelines. Below we summarize some of the general principles:

- *Keywords* Despite the fact that FNCs can be very specific, any convention should be consistent, unique, and meaningful ([Crowder et al., 2015](#)). This can be achieved by selecting appropriate keywords for file names, considering the aim of data retrieval. These keywords often include references to the content (theme/specimen) and commonly used acronyms.
- *Dates* Including consistent date formatting within the file name, following the [ISO 8601](#) standard on communication of date and time-related data, increases the findability and provides an overview of the history of the data. Specific formats for dates, such as YYYYMMDD or YYMMDD, ensure that files are listed in chronological order, even when spanning across multiple years.

- *Version numbers* Including consistent version control in file names is crucial for tracking modifications effectively. Commonly used labels like DEF, DEF1, REALLYDEF, or FINAL can lead to confusion about the latest version and make it difficult to keep track of changes between files. By incorporating version numbers within your FNC, such as v05 or v023 with leading zeros, clarity is established regarding the order of versions. This ensures accurate identification of the most recent file and facilitates efficient version management within a project or dataset. Note that including version numbering in file names is not a substitute for the use of a proper version control system.
- *Numbering* When employing a sequential numbering system for file names using zero-padding (e.g., 001, 002, 010, 011 instead of 1, 2, 10, 11, etc.) leads to a consistent width and ensures that files are correctly arranged in sequential order. This practice enhances organization and simplifies the identification of files within a numerical series. Occasionally, it may be convenient to combine it with a preceding string of characters (e.g., sub001) to prevent some software or programming language from erroneously removing the leading zeros or from considering the subject identifier as numbers instead of a categorical variable when passing this information to a statistical analysis.
- *Processed data* In some research fields, there may be many intermediate files generated from the raw data in order to obtain so-called *derivative* files that can be directly analyzed (e.g., due to cleaning, filters, validations, annotations or other manipulations). In those cases, it is useful to define suffixes that indicate what processing steps were applied (*raw* versus *derivative* files).
- *File name length* To maintain meaningful filenames, it is important to strike a balance between necessary information and brevity. Windows and macOS-based machines typically have limitations on path name length, ranging from 255 to 260 characters (Crowder et al., 2015). When including all metadata into file and folder names leads to an excess of this limit it is necessary to store some of the meta data in additional files stored at the same location while still using unique file path identifiers. The fraction of meta data contained directly in the file path vs. in the meta data file has to be adapted to the concrete needs of human readability of the information, see also below.
- *Avoid white space characters in file names* The recommendation not to use spaces in filenames comes from the danger that they might be misinterpreted, for example in shell scripting applications. This may also depend on the operating system being used, for example spaces in UNIX require a special character to be read properly. White space can be avoided by various options, see below.
- *Avoid additional dots in file names* A dot separates the file name and the extension. Additional dots in the file name make it unclear what the extension is. Some software has difficulties reading file names with more than one dot, and expects the extension already after the first dot.

Human-readable or machine-readable?

An FNC can be designed to be either human- or machine-readable, both approaches implying advantages and disadvantages (Devenyi et al., 2019) and both naturally requiring that each file (path) has a unique identifier. Human-readable FNCs focus on simplicity, clarity for human interpretation, descriptive labels, and flexibility for users to choose meaningful names. Whereas machine-readable FNCs prioritize structured formats, complexity to accommodate machine processing, uniqueness through identifiers or codes, and adherence to standards. It is important to consider the specific requirements and goals of a given project when determining which type of FNC is most appropriate. In practice, it is possible to combine filename parts that are expected to be machine-readable (e.g., to perform an initial filter or selection of files) and some are expected to be mostly read by humans. Depending on the

data modalities, it can be helpful to streamline the file naming process with a file naming generator. It will increase the efficiency of the process and reduce the errors of manual insertion.

How to avoid white space?

Several case styles used to delimitate separate parts or words in filenames without using white space. Potential limitations of the operating systems and specific software tools should be considered. One option is to write file names without spaces and capitalize each word, known as *camelCase* (e.g., Java, Kotlin). Another style, *PascalCase* (derived from the Pascal programming language), capitalizes the first letter of each word. In practice, these terms are often used interchangeably. In machine-readable cases, however, it is advisable to avoid relying on letter case, since this can pose challenges for machine-readability in some operating systems. An option for this is using underscores as in the *snake_case* (Python) or hyphens as in the *kebab-case*. Some FNCs may suggest a combination of both underscores and hyphens. It is worth noting that *kebab-case* may be misinterpreted as a date or minus sign by certain software, making the *snake_case* a recommended choice to avoid such scenarios.

How to document an FNC?

Irrespective the FNC complexity, formatting rules and file identifiers need to be clearly documented. Keeping this documentation in a central location with version control (e.g., in the project main repository or website) avoids unnecessary duplicates and ensures that any changes in the FNC reaches the collaborators. More complex projects will require more detailed documentation on metadata, folder structure, data types, etc. Ideally, this document should be as brief as possible and written in a language accessible to users, according to the three expertise levels on the project as mentioned above.

Practical use cases

Creating an FNC for projects with only a few file types can be relatively easy. However, in more complex projects, it might be best to base FNCs upon existing conventions in the field. If guidelines are used by the broader community, following these will facilitate replicability. Established guidelines can be used as templates with minor adaptations to define a project-specific FNC. Different projects ask for different types of FNCs, two use cases of templates from different domains are described in the following. The described cases below are from real world projects and thus serve a specific purpose for the users. They provide good examples of FNCs but do not necessarily comply with all the best practices listed above.

Case 1: A simple FNC

The [Vietnamese American Oral History project](#) (VAOHP) aims to capture the oral histories of first generation Vietnamese Americans who have memories of life in Vietnam, the Vietnam War, and the displacement and resettlement of refugees from Vietnam. The project team gathers audio and video recordings, as well as transcripts of interviews and photographs. The website of the project includes a *Resources* section, offering a place for students, teachers, and researchers to begin working with oral history interviews as historical evidence. The section includes the *Viet Stories Protocol packet* with extensive documentation for both contributors and users. The packet provides a separate website with [file naming guidelines](#). The FNC can be considered a simple case as it describes two main data types (audio tracks and videos) and few additional file types (documents, logs and photographs). In addition, the collected files do not require further modifications, which would complicate an FNC. In this FNC the filenames start with the project acronym VAOHP followed by a unique numeric identifier of the narrator and, separated by underscore, a suffix with a sequence number preceded by a letter indicating the file type: T (for audio tracks), V (for videos), P (for photographs), etc. See an example in [Figure 1](#). The guidelines further describe naming when there are multiple sessions of one recording or multiple sessions and recordings (e.g., VAOHP0000.1_T01, VAOHP0000.1_T02, VAOHP0000.2_T01,

etc). Suffixes for other types of files are also described, for example in VAOHP0000_L01 the L indicates this is a time log. No file extensions are specified in the guidelines.

However, this case displays two issues that should be noted. First, it proposes to use dots as separators in the filename, which can lead to difficulties with some software. Second, the lack of guidelines regarding extension and file formats may affect interoperability, for instance, if videos are uploaded in a format that has limited compatibility across systems. Our recommendation here would be to replace the additional dots with underscore and letters (e.g., VOPHP000_S01_T01 would indicate session 1) and to include specific guidelines about the recommended formats for the different types of data, e.g., .mp4 files are often used for videos since they can be read in most platforms and devices. More extensive guidelines could also include technical details that may concern audio and video quality, like sampling rate or file encoding and compression.

Figure 1: FNC of the Vietnamese American Oral History project.

Case 2: A complex FNC

The [Brain Imaging Data Structure](#) (BIDS) describes data organization in different modalities of human brain imaging research. BIDS is encouraged by a growing number of repositories and toolboxes. It describes not only file names, but also folder structure, file formats and metadata. Conveniently, these are broad guidelines that allow flexibility and can be adjusted for a given project using similar data. Numbered versions are kept in public repositories and the user community can propose changes and extensions. BIDS can be considered a complex FNC as it describes guidelines for projects that include many different data types, e.g., categories of brain images depending on the technique used, i.e., magnetic resonance, electroencephalography, microscopy, etc.

The general BIDS FNC and some examples are shown in Figure 2. The filenames consist of a chain of *entities* and a *suffix* separated by underscore, and an *extension*. The entities are a *key* (an abbreviated name) and a *value* separated by a hyphen. For example, in the file `sub-01_task-rest_eeg.edf` the entities are *subject* (abbreviated as *sub*) and *task*. The suffix *eeg* and the extension *.edf* indicate the imaging modality and the file format. Following this principle, BIDS describes entities and suffixes specific to each modality as well as those modality-independent. Thus, the FNC is integrated in a larger scheme of data and metadata organization. The extensive BIDS documentation is hosted [online](#) and created with [Read the Docs](#), an open source tool specifically designed for hosting technical documentation with version control. The BIDS principles are thoroughly described in several journal publications (e.g., [Pernet et al., 2019](#); [Bourget et al., 2022](#)) and publicly available video lectures. Beyond file naming, BIDS provides an excellent illustration of current efforts to improve data management in some research domains. Filenames can convey complex information. BIDS describes a very general scheme for all types of data. Some types might require additional suffixes and have more complex names.

General naming convention

key1-value1_key2-value2_suffix.extension

Entities describing file content. Formatted with a 'key' abbreviating followed by '-' and its value. For example, entities can describe subject, task, session, data types, etc.

A limited number of suffixes depending on the type of data. Some entities may require specific suffixes

BIDS example 1

subject 01 data type abbreviation (electroencephalography)

sub-01_task-rest_eeg.edf

recording at rest European Data Format

BIDS example 2

subject 06 task description Blood Oxygenation Level Dependent (functional magnetic resonance data)

sub-06_ses-test_task-overtverbal_bold.nii

recording from a 'test' session format: NIFTI (Neuroimaging Informatics Technology Initiative)

Figure 2: The BIDS FNC described by a general naming scheme and examples from different file types.

Take home message

Creating an FNC can be an arbitrary process to some degree, as there are no gold standards (Devenyi et al., 2019). However, there are some common principles and good practices in data organization to keep in mind. As mentioned earlier, it is recommended to begin by discussing the challenges and potential solutions, aiming to reach an unanimous agreement on a project's FNC. Since renaming files during or after data collection poses significant challenges and risks of data loss it is of crucial importance to establish an FNC prior to commencing data collection. This proactive step is a necessary component of a comprehensive Data Management Plan, ensuring efficient organization and retrieval of data (Blumer et al., 2020). To sum up, FNCs are an indispensable component to any high-quality research project irrespective of the academic domain.

More information

For specific question on FNCs you can contact the UZH library (data@ub.uzh.ch).

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